

Follow-up investigation in Hanö Bay 2024 — Condensed English summary (no figures/tables)

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About this document

This English file is a condensed analytical summary. All figures and tables are contained in the Swedish report (version of record) provided in a separate Zenodo record. References such as SE-Fig. X and SE-Tab. X point to the numbering in the Swedish report.

How to cite

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Executive summary

We followed up on historical pollution effects and a recent oil spill in Hanö Bay by assessing amphipod health (embryo aberrations, biomarkers) and genotoxic stress (DNA adducts). Sediments were analysed using a combined target/suspect/non-target workflow to characterise contaminant sources and their links to biological effects.

Key findings (refer to the Swedish report for figures/tables):

- Contaminants: Higher loads at Hanö Bay; group separation in chemical profiles (SE-Fig. 3–4). A total of 55 substances were quantified and 52 identified by suspect screening (SE-Tab. A2–A3).
- Biomarkers & genotoxicity: Amphipods from Hanö Bay showed deteriorated oxidative status, inhibited AChE, and elevated DNA adducts (SE-Fig. 5–7; SE-Tab. 3).
- Reproduction: Higher embryo malformation frequencies and share of affected females at Hanö Bay; ReproIND indicates GES not achieved (SE-Fig. 8; SE-Tab. 3).
- Oil spill link: dbRDA and diagnostic ratios indicate a shift in PAH composition 2016→2024 consistent with oil-derived inputs (SE-Fig. 10–11). Alkyl-PAHs were elevated at Hanö Bay (SE-Fig. A5).

Overall conclusion: Hanö Bay currently fails to achieve Good Environmental Status based on amphipod reproductive health.

Context and objectives

Earlier investigations showed high embryo malformations in *Monoporeia affinis* (2012) and extensive reproductive damage (2016). A large oil spill occurred on 22 October 2023 near Pukavik Bay. The 2024 study updated amphipod health status and linked pollutant profiles to biological effects (SE-Tab. 1; SE-Fig. 1–2).

Materials and methods (condensed)

Sampling (23 January 2024) at four Hanö Bay stations (T/H, H2–H4) and reference stations (HAE3, 6004, 6025, 6022; Gryt1 in 2024 and 6025 in 2023 for embryo data) (SE-Tab. 1; SE-Fig. 2). Sediments extracted (acetone/n-hexane) and analysed by GC + high-resolution MS with integrated target, suspect, and non-target screening. Diagnostic PAH ratios and alkyl-PAHs were used to infer sources (SE-Fig. 11).

Embryo analysis followed ICES guidelines and ReproIND thresholds; females dissected and embryos staged (SE-Tab. 2). Biomarkers in *Pontoporeia femorata* assessed oxidative stress, metabolism, and neurotoxicity (TBARS, ORAC/TBARS, AChE). DNA adduct profiles quantified as genotoxicity indicators (SE-Fig. 6–7).

Statistics: GLMs (area effect, protein covariate), PCoA/PERMANOVA for profile separation, SIMPER, DistLM with dbRDA to link contaminants to biological responses (SE-Tab. 3–4; SE-Tab. A5; SE-Fig. 4, 10).

Results (condensed)

Chemistry: Hanö Bay stations separate clearly from reference stations (SE-Fig. 4). Elevated PAHs (including alkyl-PAHs), PCBs, PBDEs, and OCs at Hanö Bay (SE-Fig. 3). Suspect screening highlighted PAHs and PCNs; other groups include UV filters, phthalates, pharmaceuticals (SE-Fig. A1–A2).

Biomarkers: *Pontoporeia femorata* shows a distinct Hanö Bay biomarker profile with higher oxidative stress (TBARS), AChE inhibition, and altered RNA-based metabolism (SE-Fig. 5; SE-Tab. 3).

DNA adducts: Levels higher at Hanö Bay for most adducts; 8-oxo-dG and OH- ϵ -dC differ the most (SE-Fig. 6–7).

Reproduction: Higher embryo malformation frequencies and more affected females at Hanö Bay; ReproIND indicates GES not met at H-stations while reference sites generally meet GES (SE-Fig. 8; SE-Tab. 3).

Link to oil spill: dbRDA indicates a shift in PAH composition at Hanö Bay from 2016→2024; diagnostic ratios do not show clear bunker oil residues in 2024, but elevation in alkyl-PAHs and increases in PHE, FLT, PYR, CHR suggest mixed oil-derived inputs (SE-Fig. 10–11).

Interpretation and limitations

DistLM points to PAHs (incl. alkyl-PAHs), OCs, PCBs, PBDEs, and OPEs as primary classes linked to biological effects, though 30–60% of variation remains unexplained (SE-Tab. 4; SE-Tab. A5). Limited station overlap between 2016 and 2024, patchy amphipod distributions, and multi-source pollution complicate attribution.

Data availability

Primary datasets and analytical details are described in Appendix A of the Swedish report; manuscripts by Shi et al. (2024a, 2024b) are available as preprints (see Swedish report for references).

Concordance: figures & tables (Swedish → English)

ID (SE)	English caption (short)	Where to find in Swedish PDF
SE-Fig. 1	Study overview and workflow	Figur 1
SE-Fig. 2	Sampling stations (Hanö Bay & reference)	Figur 2
SE-Fig. 3	Sediment concentrations for major contaminant classes	Figur 3
SE-Fig. 4	PCoA separation by chemical profiles	Figur 4
SE-Fig. 5	PCoA separation by biomarker profiles	Figur 5
SE-Fig. 6	Relative levels of eight DNA adducts	Figur 6
SE-Fig. 7	PCoA separation by DNA adducts	Figur 7
SE-Fig. 8	ReproIND status assessment	Figur 8
SE-Fig. 9	Embryo malformation proportions	Figur 9
SE-Fig. 10	dbRDA: PAH composition change 2016→2024	Figur 10

SE-Fig. 11	PAH diagnostic ratios & congener concentrations	Figur 11
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SE-Tab. 2	Effect variables / indicators	Tabell 2
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SE-Tab. A2	Quantified substance concentrations	Bilaga A, Tabell A2
SE-Tab. A3	Suspect-screened substances	Bilaga A, Tabell A3
SE-Tab. A4	PERMANOVA results	Bilaga A, Tabell A4
SE-Tab. A5	DistLM/dbRDA outputs	Bilaga A, Tabell A5